

PRACTICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE ADAPTATION OF FOLKLORE SONGS IN THE BUKHARA-SAMARKAND ROUTE TO MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS

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Annotation: The role and importance of Uzbek folk songs in Bukhara-Samarkand music style was explained through Uzbek folk songs and examples of notes.

Key words: music, folklore, rhythm, harmony, articulation, terma.

Such variability and multi-layered nature of folklore works makes it difficult to check many of their samples in connection with certain periods. That's why comments about the state and development of one or another genre in a certain period are approximate in most cases, of course. Based on the existing investigations, it can be said that in the most ancient times, myths, legends about clans, tribes, sayings, customs, seasons and rituals, labor songs were widespread in most peoples. During the formation of the first states, heroic epics were created, later epic, lyrical and historical songs, oral drama appeared. Traditional examples of folklore recorded in later times are mainly works created in the 6th-20th centuries. It is possible to study some examples of folklore works, the further development and status of some genres in connection with certain periods. For example, almost no written information has been preserved about the ancient forms of Uzbek epics,

several generations of folk singers who passed it down from generation to generation, and the epics they performed.

During the 17th and 18th centuries, there were very serious developments in the development of epics. The 19th century was its most flourishing period, and it spread widely among the people. In this period, certain genres, especially seasonal-ritual songs, which appeared in the earlier stages of the development of folk art, were preserved for a long time with some changes in Uzbek folklore. Some changes took place in fairy tales and riddles: their connection with totemistic views became much weaker and began to acquire a more allegorical character. A number of new genres (lyrical and historical songs, anecdotes and praises, askiya and oral drama) appeared. Thus, during this period, many works were created in almost all genres of Uzbek folk art. These works are closely related to great upheavals and important historical events in the cultural life of our people.

The historical path of our nation, the socio-political processes that have passed through it, became an important ground for the fruitfulness of the folklore. In the ethnic way of life of the Uzbek people, weddings, maraka ceremonies, traditions related to their occurrence have a historical basis.

In the process of the transition from matriarchy to patriarchy, the appearance of marriage and family forms, the emergence of a monotonous family form due to the development of the household, the formation and social significance of wedding ceremonies, the introduction of the bride-groom order, and material interest in appeared. nA wedding is a long-lasting ceremony of both formal and symbolic importance, which includes several customs and traditions, in which there are ritual songs, dances, There is a lot of ethnographic information about the fact that games, rituals, and udums turn into mass events, which ultimately end with the formation of a single family by two young people, serving to ensure the continuity of generations.

One of the important features of the Bukhara-Samarkand style is that folk songs are performed in Uzbek and Tajik languages. Due to the tradition of bilingualism, they differ from other music styles, sing some folk songs in both Uzbek and Tajik languages, and show their unique expressions.

In the performance and popularization of Uzbek folk tunes in the direction of Bukhara-Samarkand on the dutor instrument, through advanced performance methods that develop musical intuition, a unique individual image and the strengthening of emotional temperament in the performance situation, folk music, national culture in the hearts of the young generation. love is formed.

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